

Makalenin Türü / Article Type : Araştırma Makalesi / Research Article
Geliş Tarihi / Date Received : 31.01.2023
Kabul Tarihi / Date Accepted : 17.12.2023
Yayın Tarihi / Date Published : 31.12.2023
Yayın Sezonu / Pub Date Season : Güz / Autumn

Research of the Usage of Creative Drama Method In 7th Grade English Teaching in Terms of Student Attitudes and Opinions

Akgül ÇAKIROĞLU * Derya GÖĞEBAKAN YILDIZ**

Keywords:

*Creative drama,
Attitude towards
English lesson,
Student opinions*

ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to examine the effect of creative drama in English teaching in terms of students' attitudes and opinions. The study group consists of 8 students attending the 7th grade of a public secondary school. The English course "Sports" and "Biography" units were taught in a 6-week period with the prepared creative drama method learning draft. Case study was used in the research. In the study, quantitative and qualitative data were collected together. Quantitative data were obtained from the student attitude scale and qualitative data were obtained from student opinions. In this research, quantitative data were analyzed with non-parametric Mann Whitney U for related samples. Descriptive analysis was used in the analysis of qualitative data. The findings obtained from the attitude scale in the study showed that creative drama activities positively affected students' attitudes towards the English lesson. When the interviews with the students were analyzed, it was concluded that the drama method made the lesson fun, increased the learning motivation for the lesson, and could be effective in learning foreign language vocabulary and pronunciation.

7. Sınıf İngilizce Dersi Öğretiminde Yaratıcı Drama Yöntemi Kullanımının Öğrenci Tutumları ve Görüşleri Açısından İncelenmesi

Anahtar Kelimeler:

*Yaratıcı drama,
İngilizce dersine
yönelik tutum,
öğrenci görüşleri,*

ÖZ

Bu çalışmanın amacı, İngilizce dersini Yaratıcı Drama Yöntemiyle işlemenin öğrenci tutum ve görüşleri üzerinde etkisini araştırmaktır. Çalışma grubunu bir devlet ortaokulunun 7. sınıfına devam eden 8 öğrenci oluşturmaktadır. İngilizce dersi "Sports" ve "Biography" üniteleri yaratıcı drama yöntemiyle hazırlanan dersplanlarıyla 6 haftalık süre zarfında işlenmiştir. Araştırmada yöntem olarak durum çalışması kullanılmıştır. Çalışmada nicel ve nitel veriler birlikte toplanmıştır. Nicel veriler öğrenci tutum ölçeğinden ve nitel veriler ise öğrenci görüşlerinden elde edilmiştir. Nicel veriler ilişkili örneklem non-parametrik Mann Whitney U testi ile analiz edilmiştir. Nitel verilerin analizinde betimsel analiz kullanılmıştır. Araştırmada tutum ölçeğinden elde edilen bulgular yaratıcı drama etkinliklerinin öğrencilerin İngilizce dersine yönelik tutumlarını olumlu yönde etkilediğini göstermiştir. Öğrencilerle yapılan görüşmeler analiz edildiğinde ise drama yönteminin dersi eğlenceli hale getirdiği derse yönelik öğrenme isteğini artırdığı, yabancı dilde kelime ve telaffuz öğreniminde etkili etkili olabileceği sonucuna ulaşılmıştır.

* Doç.Dr. Manisa Celal Bayar Üniversitesi, Eğitim Fakültesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Bölümü/ Anabilim Dalı, derya.yildiz@cbu.edu.tr
* Öğretmen, MEB, akglaltnkynk@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Language is one of the most important communication tools in the globalizing world. People can communicate in a foreign language. Due to the importance of knowing a foreign language in the world, foreign language teaching has become an important focal point among countries. Foreign language teaching has become a subject of great importance in Turkey in recent years. Turkey has made great efforts on foreign language teaching, and significant time and resources have been spent on this subject both by the public and individually (Niğdelioğlu and Altun, 2018). However, in general, it was seen that the expected level of success in foreign language teaching could not be achieved (Demirel, 1999). In order to find a solution to the problems experienced in foreign language teaching, attention should be paid to the change process of the individual and society by knowing the characteristics of the period in which it is lived. The change process of the society also significantly affects the field of education. These changes have left the place of the traditional method in the learning process to the educational approach that puts the individual in the center. In student-centered approaches, the learner is an active part of learning. Student-centered approaches aim to keep learning from being separated from student life and to prioritize the interests and needs of the learner (Demirel, 1997).

It is not possible to expect students to learn a foreign language effectively in a learning environment where only one teacher teaches the lesson and the student only listens to the lesson during the lesson. If students actively participate in the learning process, a learning environment can be created easily. One of the methods that increase the active participation of the student in the lesson is drama. Creative drama is one of the methods that includes the learner in the learning process, provides the learner with the opportunity to learn by doing and experiencing, helps the learner to realize himself, to be a creative and productive individual, in short, to develop the life skills of the individual (Kaf, 2000). In this case, "based on the life experiences of the individuals forming a group, a purpose, thought, improvisation, role playing, etc. we can call it creative drama, which is animated by using techniques. While these activity processes are carried out in the company of an instructor, it is based on the principle of here and now, acting on the individual's own instinct, and this method is fed by the general features of the game" (Adıgüzel, 2018, p. 43).

Likewise, "Creative drama as a technique, by making use of activities such as improvisation, animation, role playing, in the form of group work by the participants, internalizing a situation, event, or concept by reviving them in old play activities, making a meaning" (San, 2008) definable. Creative drama, which is a method that involves students in the process and puts the student in the center, is of great importance in English teaching in order to facilitate students' foreign language learning and to ensure their active participation in the lesson. "The effective use of creative drama activities in accordance with their purpose provides significant benefits in the development of individuals' language skills" (Aykaç & Çetinkaya, 2013). Drama makes English teaching a method that takes it away from being a lesson and just memorizing words. With the roles assigned to them, students; they learn to use language, thought, emotion and behavior together in the classroom environment (Paker, 2006). The use of drama method in English lessons enables students to use English as they use their own language in daily life and contributes to their learning and development by keeping it in their memory (Tulving, 1985). As can be seen, the creative drama method is very useful in this regard, as foreign language learning has a strong relationship with experience. People can learn a foreign language only if they have the chance to practice it. For this reason, people living in a foreign country can learn the mother tongue of that country in a short time.

In this context, the creative drama method provides an environment for students to learn by doing and experiencing what they have learned during the learning period, to make what they learn permanent and to associate what they learn with the topics they will study in the future, to develop speaking skills and collaborative actions, and has an important place in terms of turning them into skills. The English lesson, which is taught with drama activities, will motivate students to communicate in the target language, which is the skill they have the most difficulty with, and will

enable them to participate actively in the learning process. Based on this situation, in line with the explanations, this study aimed to find out whether creative drama would encourage students' attitude and motivation towards the lesson due to its significant contributions to language learning. This study is important as there is no study in the literature that analyzes the effect of creative drama on the attitude and motivation of 7th grade students. For this reason, the information to be obtained from this study is important in terms of shedding light on other studies that are likely to be done in the future.

In this context, the research seeks answers to the following questions:

In the Foreign Language course;

1. Did the teaching of the "Sports" and "Biography" units in the 7th grade textbook with the creative drama method affect the attitudes of the students towards the lesson?

2. What are the students' views on the use of creative drama technique as an activity in the lesson in order to learn the subjects in the "Sports" and "Biography" units in the 7th grade textbook?

The aim of this study is to examine the creative drama activities used as a method in the English lesson of the "Sports" and "Biography" units in the 7th grade textbook in order to reach the attitudes and opinions of the students towards the lesson and to define the effective applications. The studies (Miccoli, 2003; Turkewych & Divido, 1978; Yeager, 1989) revealed that the creative drama method is a method that affects language teaching. In this research proposal, the effect of teaching with creative drama method on students' attitudes and views towards the lesson will be interpreted. For this reason, the information to be obtained from this study is important in terms of shedding light on other studies that are likely to be done in the future.

1.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Creative Drama

There are many studies investigating the use of drama as a teaching tool. The aim of this study is to investigate to what extent students' attitudes and perspectives towards the English lesson are affected by the use of teaching words and reinforcing the taught subjects through drama activities when the lesson is taught with the creative drama method. Creative drama is one of the drama techniques used in the field of education. Dewey's "learning by doing" theory supports the inclusion of creative drama in the field of education (Ayna& Günday, 2021). Particularly, the contribution of children by their active participation in learning processes cannot be denied (Gönen & Dalkılıç, 1999). Creative drama method is used in the field of education by making use of techniques such as role-playing and improvisation while processing any subject. Students make animations based on their knowledge and experience (Adıgüzel, 2006). Creative drama, which is an important part of teaching, is seen as an effective way for students to express themselves comfortably without limiting (Aytaş, 2008). Creative drama as a method aims to train students who are sensitive, aware of everything, who are aware of their responsibilities in harmony with their friends, who aim to learn by doing and experiencing, to make the learning process effective (Karaosmanoğlu, 2015).

Each student has a dream world of his own, drama activities help students develop their own inner world in language acquisition. Thanks to drama, safe environments are created where students can easily express themselves in another language. "Students become more willing to learn with creative drama activities. Students who are alone in the classroom mingle with other students and create a friendly atmosphere" (Dirim, 2002, pp. 54-55). Using the drama method also increases students' motivation towards the lesson (Tokdemir, 2015). The creative drama activity makes the lesson fun and enables students to make the information they learn in the lesson more permanent. In the studies that students do with their classmates, activities are carried out in the form of process-oriented studies, not results, by providing opportunities for the development of skills such as communication skills within the group, understanding each other, being in harmony with each other,

and creating a sense of mutual respect and trust (Göktürk, Çalışkan & Öztürk, 2020). According to Rastelli (2006), the drama method in learning English helps students to improve their speaking skills by improving communication, motivation, cooperation and teamwork. In this context, we can say that drama activities increase communication among students and contribute to the development of speaking skills. While exhibiting creative drama activities in the classroom, there is no audience because all students participate in drama activities and take an active role in foreign language learning (Erdoğan, 2016). Thanks to the fact that drama activities create a stress-free and fun environment, it makes it easier for students to speak English (Göktürk, 2019). When they realize that there is nothing to be ashamed of, they focus more on learning the language and continue their speaking activities (Hamilton & McLeod, 1993). As can be seen from the studies, creative drama activities affect students' attitudes towards the lesson by providing students with the ability to express themselves, providing an effective interaction environment, and increasing students' self-confidence.

Attitude

In this section, the definitions of the concept of attitude, which constitutes an important state of awareness, will be discussed. Attitude is a cognitive, behavioral and emotional predisposition that a person brings together on the basis of his/her lived experience, knowledge and feelings about any object, subject or event (İnceoğlu, 2010). According to Demirel (1993), attitude; "It is a learned disposition that compels a person to behave in certain ways in the face of certain people, situations, and things." According to this definition, we can say that attitude is a situation that shapes the behavior of a person and directs how he should behave towards anything, object or person. On the other hand, according to Keskin (2003) mentioned; Attitude is the way a person takes a stand against objects or subjects that have a psychological value. Attitudes; values, norms and relations of societies. People perform their behaviors according to their attitudes in their relations with other individuals. For example, someone who gives importance to the honesty of the other person behaves honestly both in his own behavior and in his relationship with those around him (Aydoslu, 2005). A movie, a book, a teacher, a word, etc. It is the attitude, stance or behavior style exhibited against (İnceoğlu, 2010). In this context, it can be said that the students formed a new attitude towards the lessons taught with the drama method. For example, the way in which the student understands his class, friends, teacher or the experiences he has acquired in a lesson greatly affect his attitude towards learning a foreign language. Because everything that students perceive affects their behavior and attitudes towards the lesson.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research model

The case study, which is one of the qualitative research designs, was used in the study. According to Yin (2003, 13-14), the case study is a comprehensive research strategy used in real-life conditions of a current phenomenon, in situations where the existing context and the phenomenon are intertwined, and a large number of data sources are accessed. Research data were provided with both quantitative and qualitative data collection tools. An attitude scale in the form of pre-test and post-test was applied to measure the effect of activities based on creative drama method, which includes the quantitative dimension of the research, on learning the English lesson. In the qualitative dimension, a student interview form was used to learn the thoughts of the students on creative drama activities.

2.2. Study group

The research was carried out in a public secondary school affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in the province of Manisa in the fall semester of the 2022-2023 academic year. The participants of the research consist of 8 students, 4 girls and 4 boys, studying in the 7th grade.

2.3. Data collection tools

To collect data in the research; "Attitude Scale Towards English Lesson", which was created by Aydoslu (2005) in order to measure students' attitudes towards foreign language lessons, was used to measure students' attitudes towards foreign language lessons, at the beginning and end of the research. In addition, "Student Interview Form on the Application of Creative Drama Method" was used.

2.4. Implementation process

In this study, creative drama activities were prepared and applied in order to reach students' attitudes and views towards the English lesson. The study was carried out in the second (Sports) and third (Biographies) units of the Secondary School English Curriculum. The course outcomes of the second and third units (Appendix 1) were reviewed. A lesson plan (Appendix 2) consisting of creative drama activities was prepared in order to transfer these gains to the students. The research was carried out in a six-week period in the first semester of the 2022-2023 academic year. The students answered the pre-tests in the first week. Students were informed about how to answer the attitude scale. The attitude scale was answered by the students. Before starting the application process, the students were informed that the determined "Sports" and "Biography" units would be taught with the Creative Drama method, and during this period, they should come to the lesson prepared by learning the unit words given at the beginning of the unit. After the completion of these processes in the first week, the creative drama application process was started. The application lasted for 6 weeks and the lesson plans were implemented. 4 hours of the English lesson, which is 6 lesson hours per week, was devoted to creative drama activities, and the remaining 2 lesson hours were taught to the students about the unit, structural elements and the test was solved. Lesson plans including creative drama activities were applied in order to determine whether it would have an effect on students' attitudes towards the English lesson.

The stages of creative drama were applied in the form of preparation and warm-up at the beginning of the lesson, followed by the animation and finally the evaluation. Different creative drama activities were held every week. Creative drama activities such as role playing, event animation, snapwords, poetry recital, and word hunt were applied. At the end of the sixth week, the students were given a post-test. Opinions of the students were taken with the Student Interview Form on the Application of Creative Drama Method. 5 open-ended questions were prepared to get students' opinions on this subject. With these questions, students' opinions about the effect of using the creative drama method in the English lesson and the difficulties faced by the students during the application period were taken. For the analysis of pre-test and post-test data, the data were analyzed using the SPSS statistical program.

Sample Application (2. Lesson of the Week)

The learning outcomes of the course are as follows: Talks about sports, Talks about routines and daily activities, explains what people do regularly, makes explanatory and reasoned sentences (MEB, 2018). In this activity, which lasted four lesson hours, the Word Box game was played. First, the students presented the school's sports equipment in English, then the words of the 'Sports' unit were written in the box prepared by the students. The students were divided into groups as 4 girls and 4 boys. First, the teacher asked the students the word, and one of the group who knew it started the game by getting on the board and had his friends find the word he chose from the word box with the pantomime technique. Whichever group knows wins points. Then, as part of the Snapword activity, colored papers were distributed to the students by the teacher and the students drew the words of the unit on the paper with their creative thoughts. Snapword events are posted on the clipboard. At the end of the lesson, students' opinions were taken during the evaluation and discussion stage. Students stated that they enjoyed the activities very much and had fun. They said that the lesson was over very quickly and they would be happier if they studied all the lessons in this way.

2.5. Data analysis method

SPSS statistical program was used for the analysis of the pretest-posttest data to be obtained from the data collection tools. The data obtained in line with the objectives of the study were analyzed using SPSS-29.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) in computer environment. The Mann Whitney U test was used to understand whether there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the Attitudes towards English Lesson Scale. The data obtained from the student interviews were analyzed using qualitative analysis techniques. Descriptive analysis was used in direct quotations (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). Students were coded as S1, S2....S7, S8.

3. FINDINGS

In this section, the research question is "What is the effect of teaching foreign language lessons with Creative Drama method on students' attitudes and opinions?" The data are explained in a way to answer the question. In this study, in which the use of creative drama technique has an effect on the attitudes of the students in the Foreign Language course, the data obtained from the scale used in the students were interpreted and evaluated. A five-point Likert scale (I totally disagree (1), I disagree (2), I am undecided (3), I agree (4), I totally agree (5)) was used in the interpretation of the data related to the "Attitude Scale towards English Lesson". Five open-ended questions prepared by the teacher were asked to get the opinions of the students about the lesson taught with the drama method. Analysis results are presented under the headings of "attitude towards the course" and "student opinions".

3.1. Attitude towards the English lesson

The findings obtained from the Attitude Scale towards Speaking English, which was applied before and after the "Sports and Biographies" unit in order to measure the attitudes of the students, Table 1. is also shown.

Table 1: Statistical Results of Attitude Scale Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores

Test	N	S.T.	S.O.	U	Z	
Pre-Test	8	6,50	26.000		-2,337	
Post-Test	8	2,50	10.000	36.000	-2,309	0,029

Non-Parametric Mann Whitney U test; It was used to reveal the attitude differences of students towards the English lesson before they started drama activities (pre-test) and after they started (post-test). According to the results of the analysis, the non-parametric Mann Whitney U test result was 0.029, and since it was less than 0.050, there was a statistically significant difference in terms of students' attitude scores. From this result, we can say that students' attitudes towards the English lesson have developed positively.

3.2. Student opinions

At the end of the process, five open-ended questions were asked to get the opinions of the students about how the lesson taught with the creative drama method went. Below are the questions and the answers given by the students to the questions. They are grouped under the given five headings. Results are shown in Table 2. The sections divided into categories in the table support the findings of attitude towards the course.

According to this result, it can be concluded that the method affects the lesson positively. The interview questions and the answers given by the students to these questions are given below.

Question 1: Do you enjoy using drama techniques such as role-playing while teaching English class? If yes, please explain.

S1: Yes, I like it because it makes it easier for me to learn English, it increases my self-confidence when I play role-playing boards, so I think it helps me and we do fun activities.

S2: Yes, because learning the English lesson becomes easier and we have a lot of fun while learning the lesson. In short, teaching through drama makes it easier for us to learn.

S3: Yes, my speaking in English class strengthens my language, raises my morale and encourages me to learn English.

S4: Yes, I feel like I am that character and we also play with my friends before our teacher comes, which helps me to understand the lesson better.

S5: Absolutely, I like it, it makes learning more enjoyable, in addition, it strengthens my speaking skills and helps me speak fluently.

S6: Yes, because it helps me understand the English lesson and develops me. We are having fun with the roles we take on and the games we play. I understand the lesson better this way.

S7: Yes, I love it. I think it would be easier and more permanent for us to learn if such activities were carried out in all classes.

S8: Yes, we have a lot of fun with my friends. The lesson ends very quickly. I'm never bored.

Question 2: Did your English teacher use the drama method as a technique in the English lesson? If yes, how did she use it?

S1: Yes, she used it. She gave us different roles according to each student's personality and then we presented them with games in class, we did snapwords, we did many activities like word finding games.

S2: Yes, through theatre, by dividing us into groups and making presentations in English.

S3: Yes, she used it. By playing games and dividing us into groups, playing games like the word box game.

S4: Yes, we played many games. Our teacher divided us into groups and each group played a game. For example, we played many games in which we presented the lesson in the form of dialogue, we played the snake game.

S5: Our teacher used drama activities. We played games and gave presentations.

S6: Yes, it was used in the lesson. With the guidance of our teacher, we held activities, competitions and speeches with my friends. This thing increases the student's self-confidence and improves their skills.

S7: Yes, our teacher always uses word games or drama to help us understand the lessons better, using this technique makes it easier for me to learn.

S8: Yes, she used it as a method. For example, a friend of ours was a poet and played him, we memorized dialogues and made presentations, we did various activities such as the word box game.

Question 3: Do you prefer the traditional way of learning English or the drama method? Explain why?

S1: I prefer the drama method because it is very entertaining, facilitates our learning and provides us with the ability to communicate better socially and personally.

S2: I prefer drama because it facilitates learning and helps the person to improve their English.

S3: I choose drama, it helps me to speak and improve my English, helps me feel confident and teaches me English through improvisation.

S4: Of course, with the drama method, because the lesson becomes more fun and enjoyable.

S5: I prefer to learn through drama, it gave me a passion for learning new things and discovering new words. Moreover, the games we played with the group strengthened the relations between me and my classmates and made me a self-confident student.

S6: Drama method, because it becomes more fun and easy for us to understand and assimilate the lesson.

S7: Drama is much more fun and enjoyable, it also strengthens my relationships with my friends.

S8: Drama because doing activities with my friends makes me more social.

Question 4: Did you have any problems in English class while applying the drama method? Please explain.

S1: Yes, it did, but very little. The positive aspects it provides us are such as increasing our self-confidence, learning new words, and doing activities in cooperation. It's like I pause when talking about negative aspects because I think I'm pronouncing it wrong.

S2: No, it didn't. We had a fun lesson.

S3: No, it didn't happen, but sometimes I laughed because I laughed a lot.

S4: Yes, I think I have problems, I can memorize a little and understand what I read.

S5: No, I used to feel shy when speaking or reading something in English, but now I have no difficulty in this matter, I overcame this situation thanks to games.

S6: Yes, I was a little nervous at first, but over time I got used to it and it became fun.

S7: No, actually, but sometimes I felt shy at first, and I got used to it when I was presenting in front of my friends.

S8: Yes, I had difficulty in reading the words.

Question 5: Do you think the drama method will increase your speaking skills? If so, how?

S1: Yes, our speaking skills can increase because we express ourselves aloud with new words, and when we do drama activities, it helped me understand English words and increase my vocabulary.

S2: Yes, the activities we talked about increased my self-confidence and I could speak even if it was wrong.

S3: Yes, because before I do drama, I work on my presentation at home and research the pronunciations and speak better and more fluently, which I like very much.

S4: Of course, I think it will increase my speaking skill. For example, when we play a game or give a speech, we make mistakes and we correct them, it becomes more permanent.

S5: Yes, I think it improved our speaking skills. In fact, it has not only improved our speaking skills, but also our other reading and comprehension skills.

S6: Yes, I think it developed, I think the role plays we played were very effective.

S7: Yes, definitely, when I talk to my friends, I notice that my English has improved and this gives me more self-confidence.

S8: Yes, it has increased my speaking skills. I have not studied this much dialogue or words until now. Now I'm better.

Table2: Analysis Results of Student Opinions

Questions Asked to Students	Answers Given by Students
Do you enjoy using drama techniques such as role-playing while teaching English? If yes, please explain.	The students' responses showed that drama techniques increased their English skills, they enjoyed learning English, and these techniques increased their self-confidence.
Did your English teacher use the drama method as a technique in the English lesson? If yes, how did she use it?	The students' answers show that the English teacher performs creative drama with games, small and large group activities in the English lesson.
Do you prefer the traditional way of learning English or the drama method? Explain why?	The students' responses showed that drama was better than the traditional way for many reasons, such as making learning English easier, gaining new skills, increasing interaction, and making learning exciting and more enjoyable.
Did you have any problems in English class while applying the drama method? Please explain.	The majority of the students' responses showed that there was no problem in the speaking lesson while playing the drama, but some students' responses showed that they encountered problems with word pronunciation, shyness, and feeling nervous, especially when performing in front of their classmates.
Do you think the drama method will increase your speaking skill? If so, how?	The students' answers showed that drama increased their speaking skills and that drama improved them.

The majority of the students' answers showed that creative drama was fun, effective in learning English, students' playing drama with their friends increased their social skills, their views on the lesson improved positively, and the creative drama method had a significant effect on students' speaking skills. In addition, his students also showed that, as Ulubey stated in 2015, the creative drama method helps students to participate actively in the learning process and increases their willingness to learn, their self-confidence and their courage.

4. RESULTS

The aim of this study was to apply creative drama activities to the students in order to obtain the attitudes of 7th grade students towards the English lesson and to investigate the effects of the applications on the students. The argument of the research was as follows: With creative drama activities, students can develop positive attitudes towards the English lesson. A positive attitude can enable students to be successful in the lesson and to participate in the lesson more willingly. With the use of creative drama in a foreign language, positive emotions can be created in the English learning process (Atas, 2015; Taşçı, 2011). Learning English can become more fun with the creative drama method. If the creative drama method is used in English teaching, it creates awareness of the culture of that language. The language learned is used a lot thanks to the creative drama method, and

improvements are observed in students' skills such as understanding, explaining and persuading the subject. In daily life, students can easily apply these skills (Aydeniz, 2012). Before starting the creative drama activities, the students were informed about the process and an attitude scale was applied. Creative drama activities were held with the relevant units of the 6-week curriculum (Sports and Biographies). At the end of the process, a post-test was made, student opinions were taken, and process evaluation was made with the students.

A number of findings emerged from this study. One of them, when the data obtained from the pre-test and post-test application of the attitude scale were interpreted, showed that the students' attitudes towards the foreign language lesson in the lesson taught with the creative drama method positively affected the students' attitudes towards the foreign language lesson and the activities performed in the lesson learning process played a constructive role supports his claim. Similar to this study, Göktürk, Çalışkan, and Öztürk's (2020) study on the effect of creative drama activities on the development of speaking skills revealed that creative drama activities improved speaking skills and positively affected students' attitudes towards the lesson, which supports my argument in this study. quality. Another study that supports this analysis is that the data obtained from students' opinions show that the learning environment is more productive by making the lesson fun, it increases the motivation of the students towards the lesson, and the method is effective in terms of vocabulary and pronunciation in foreign language learning. It has been reached that it can be effective in teaching the lesson in other lessons, especially in the language lesson. Since the students are active in the learning process, it was concluded that they both willingly learn the topics covered and successfully transform the topic they learned into a skill. In the general evaluation made with the students at the end of 6 weeks, it was stated by the students that the negative attitudes and thoughts of the students towards the lesson decreased thanks to the creative drama method. The study also demonstrated the insights of creative drama into students' self-confidence. Tuna Gündoğdu and Kartal (2021) also included student opinions in teaching English vocabulary with taboo game. From the students' opinions, similar results were obtained such as that vocabulary learning is more permanent thanks to such activities, that the activities made the lesson more enjoyable and that it facilitates the student in learning the subject, and that such activities should be applied in other lessons supports the part.

Thanks to the activities of the creative drama method, students can understand the foreign language well and associate it with their daily lives (Lakshmi & Nageswari, 2015). Creative drama creates an environment for the free expression of language in the classroom environment. It gives students the opportunity to experience a foreign language according to their own level (Demirel, 1999; Dündar, 2012; Erdoğan, 2016). As can be seen, when viewed in terms of creative drama characteristics, it is an important method in foreign language teaching. As a result of the study conducted by Göktürk (2019), it was concluded that the creative drama method improved the speaking skills of the students and that the improvement in speaking skills positively affected the students' attitudes towards their lessons. Likewise, the results of the study they conducted in Kılıç & Tuncel (2009) revealed that the creative drama method was effective in teaching and positively affected students' attitudes towards the lesson. In this context, similar studies supporting this study support that the drama method develops a positive attitude and demonstrates the positive effectiveness of the drama method. It is expected that this study will shed light on possible future studies.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- Drama activities that will attract students' attention and draw them to the lesson should be included.
 - English teaching can be removed from memorization and active participation can be ensured by including drama activities.
-

• Considering the effect of creative drama method on teaching and learning, all teachers should be informed about drama method through in-service training.

• Based on the answers given by the students in the interview questions, the creative drama method should be an indispensable technique not only in foreign language learning and teaching but also in other main courses.

• As a result of the research, it has been determined that the creative drama method has a positive development in the attitudes and opinions of the students towards the foreign language lesson. By emphasizing the use of this method in the lessons, it can be ensured that the students' interest in the lesson is kept alive and the information and learning are permanent.

REFERENCES

- Adıgüzel, H.Ö. (2006). Yaratıcı drama kavramı, bileşenleri ve aşamalar. *Yaratıcı Drama Dergisi*, 1 (1), 17-29.
- Adıgüzel, Ö. (2018). *Eğitimde yaratıcı drama*. Pegem Akademi.
- Atas, M. (2015). The reduction of speaking anxiety in EFL learners through drama techniques. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 176, 961 – 969.
- Aydeniz, H. (2012). *Yaratıcı drama yönteminin üniversite öğrencilerinin akademik başarılarına ve Fransızca konuşmaya yönelik tutumlarına etkisi* [Master's Thesis, Gazi University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Aydoslu, U. (2005). *Öğretmen Adaylarının Yabancı Dil Olarak İngilizce Dersine İlişkin Tutumlarının İncelenmesi (B.E.F. Örneği)*, [Master's Thesis, Süleyman Demirel University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Aykaç, M. & Çetinkaya, G. (2013). Yaratıcı drama etkinliklerinin Türkçe öğretmen adaylarının konuşma becerilerine etkisi. *Turkish Studies*, 8(9), 671-682.
- Ayna, D. & Günday, R. (2021). Yaratıcı drama tekniği kullanımının 8. sınıf İngilizce dersi okuma becerisinin geliştirilmesinde öğrenci tutumuna etkisi. *Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 21(4), 1378-1391.
- Aytaş, G. (2008). *Türkçe eğitiminde tematik yaratıcı drama*. Akçağ Yayınları.
- Demirel, Ö. (1993). *Yabancı dil öğretimi ilkeler, yöntemler, teknikler*. Usem Yayınları 6.
- Demirel, Ö. (1997). *Kuramdan uygulamaya eğitimde program geliştirme*. Usem Yayınları 13.
- Demirel, Ö. (1999). *İlköğretim okullarında yabancı dil öğretimi. (3.baskı)*. Milli Eğitim Basımevi.
- Dirim, A. (2002). *Okul öncesi eğitimde yaratıcı drama*. Esin Yayınevi.
- Dündar, Ş. (2012). Nine drama activities for foreign language classrooms: Benefits and challenges. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 70. 1424-1431.
- Erdoğan, C. (2016). *Yaratıcı drama yönteminin ilkokul ikinci sınıf İngilizce dersi meyveler (fruits) ünitesindeki sözcük öğrenme başarısına etkisi* [Master's Thesis, Ankara University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Gömlüksiz, M. N. (2003). İngilizce Duyuşsal Alana İlişkin Öğretmen Görüşlerinin Çeşitli Değişkenler Açısından Değerlendirilmesi. *Eğitim Araştırmaları*, 27, 69-82.
- Göktürk, Çalışkan & Öztürk (2020). The Effects Of Creative Drama Activities On Developing English Speaking Skills. *Journal of Inquiry Based Activities (JIBA)* 10,(1), 1-17.
- Göktürk, Ö. (2019). *Yaratıcı drama etkinliklerinin İngilizce konuşma becerisine etkisi*. [Master's Thesis, Necmettin Erbakan University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Gönen, M & Dalkılıç, N. U. (1999). *Çocuk eğitiminde drama: Yöntem ve uygulamalar*, Epsilon Yayıncılık.
-

- Hamilton, J. & McLeod, A. (1993). *Drama in the language classrooms*. Great Britain: Oakdale Printing Co Ltd.
- İnceođlu, M. (2010). *Tutum, algı ve iletişim*. Beykent Üniversitesi Yayınları.
- Kaf, Ö. (1999). *Hayat bilgisi dersinde bazı sosyal becerilerin kazandırılmasında yaratıcı drama yönteminin etkisi* [Master's Thesis, Çukurova University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Karaosmanođlu, G. (2015). *Yaratıcı drama yönteminin 6. sınıf bilişim teknolojileri ve yazılı dersi alan öğrencilerin ders başarılarına etkisi* [Master's Thesis, Anklara University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Keskin, A. (2003). *İlköğretim II. kademe öğrencilerinin İngilizceye yönelik tutumları ile akademik başarıları arasındaki ilişkiler* [Master's Thesis, Dokuz Eylül University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Kılıç, Ş., & Tuncel, M. (2009). Yaratıcı dramanın İngilizce konuşmaya ve tutuma etkisi. *Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 9(2), 55-81.
- Lakshmi, K., & Nageswari, R. (2015). Technology to frame English sentences: m-learning in language learning. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(6 S1), 44.
- MEB, (2018). İngilizce Dersi Öğretim Programı (İlkokul ve Ortaokul 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 ve 8. Sınıflar <http://mufredat.meb.gov.tr/Dosyalar/201812411191321-%C4%B0NG%C4%B0L%C4%B0ZCE%20%C3%96%C4%9ERET%C4%B0M%20PROGRAMI%20KIsas%C3%B6r%C3%BC.pdf>
- Miccoli, L. (2003). English through drama for oral skills development, *ELT. Journal*, 57 (2), 122-129.
- Niğdeliođlu, E. H., & Altun, S. (2018). Yabancı Dil Öğretiminde Yaratıcı Drama: Öğrenci Ürünleri ve Görüşleri Üzerine Nitel Bir Çalışma. *Researcher*, 6(1), 236-258.
- Paker, T. (2006). *İngilizce Öğretiminde Drama Etkinlikleri: Öğretmenin, Öğrencilerin Roller ve Özel PEV İlköğretim Okulu Uygulamaları*, XV. Ulusal Eğitim Bilimleri Kongresi, Muğla Üniversitesi, Eğitim Fakültesi, Muğla
- Rastelli, L. R. (2006). Drama in language learning. *Encuentro Journal of Research and Innovation in the Language Classroom*, 16, 82-94. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/58902422.pdf>
- San, İ. (2008). *Eğitimde yaratıcı drama*. Naturel Yayıncılık.
- Taşçı, F. (2011). *Anadolu liseleri İngilizce derslerinde konuşma ve dinleme becerilerinin kazandırılmasına yönelik etkinliklerde karşılaşılan istenmeyen öğrenci davranışlarının incelenmesi: öğretmen ve öğrenci algıları*, Kayseri ili örneği [Master's Thesis, Erciyes University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Tokdemir, G. (2015). *Teaching vocabulary to young learners through drama* [Master's Thesis, Çağ University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Tulving, E. (1985). Memory and consciousness. *Canadian Psychology*, 26, 1-12.
- Turkewych, C., & Divido, N. (1978, Sum). *Creative dramatics and second language learning*. TESL Talk, 09, (03).
- Tuna Gündođdu, R & Kartal, Ş (2021). Yedinci sınıf öğrencilerinin Tabu oyunu ile İngilizce kelime öğrenmeye yönelik görüşleri. *Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Eğitimi Dergisi*, 7(1), 75-101. DOI: 10.47615/issej.910488
- Ulubey, Ö. (2015). *Vatandaşlık ve demokrasi eğitimi programının yaratıcı drama ve diğer etkileşimli öğretim yöntemleri ile uygulanmasının akademik başarıya ve demokratik değerlere bağlılığa etkisi*. [Doctoral dissertation, Ankara University]. Turkish Council of Higher Education Theses Center.
- Yeager, J. (1989, Fall). Three ways to incorporate drama through storytelling in your second English class. *Drama Theatre Teacher*, 02, (01).
-

Yin, R. K. (2003). *Case study research: Design and methods* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.

Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek, H. (2016). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri*. (10.Baskı) Seçkin Yayıncılık.